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FORMATION OF READINESS FOR CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE FIELD OF AUDIOVISUAL ART AND PRODUCTION

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate and analyze the criteria and indicators of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, namely: motivational and value, cognitive and cognitive, and activity and creative. In accordance with these criteria, the work aims to prove the professional competencies that an audiovisual art and production specialist should have, which will enable a creative approach to professional activity. **The research methodology** consists in the application of the following methods: empirical research level – the method of observation, rating and self-evaluation, collective consultation, experiment, content analysis, generalization of practical experience, expert evaluation; theoretical level of research – experimental verification of new creative projects, solving integrated tasks, analytical method, deductive, inductive, modelling, comparison, abstraction and concretization, analysis and synthesis, thought (imaginary) experiment, generalization of the studied material. **Scientific novelty.** For the first time in the theory and practice of audiovisual art and production, criteria and indicators of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production have been proposed and experimentally verified. **Conclusions.** The formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production is a complex and lengthy process, the effectiveness of which is influenced by certain conditions, factors and causes. This approach identifies criteria and indicators for the formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, as well as professional competencies

that form a holistic structure in which all elements are interdependent and interrelated.

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Problem Statement

One of the determining factors of professional training and creative activity of specialists in the field of audiovisual art and production is the level of participants' professional competence in audiovisual production. It is this category of workers that ensures the organization of the creative process, the preparation of the script, and the realization of the director's idea, in addition, it is the work of operators and sound engineers, the preparation of musical accompaniment, advertising activities, etc.

The need for continuous professional development of the specified category of employees, providing them with opportunities for operational mastery of professional competencies, enables the relevant application of acquired professional skills in a creative context. Based on this, the problem of researching the process readiness formation for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production is appropriate and relevant.

Recent research and publications analysis

The phenomenon of readiness for creative activity is thoroughly reflected in the psychological and pedagogical research of O. Bartkiv (2010).

O. Bezruchko (2013; 2014a) analyzed in detail the symbiosis of experiments and traditions in training specialists in creative specialities (directors, cameramen,

announcers and TV program hosts) in a Ukrainian higher education establishment of artistic orientation.

V. Uruskyi determined that there is a readiness for creative activity, manifested through the ability to identify the most effective methods and ways of introducing innovations, mastery of the implemented technologies, and methods, etc.

The dominant factors of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production were studied by O. Priadko (2015).

The analysis of the results of the research activity on the motivational and value criterion in forming readiness for creative action in audiovisual art and production is substantiated by O. Malukhin (2005).

He described in detail the five stages of a pedagogical experiment with young screenwriters at one of the Kyiv universities that train specialists for film and television. O. Bezruchko (2019).

H. Pohrebniak (2022) studied the current problems of contemporary directing education in Ukraine. The author outlined the problems of training film and television directors in the field of screen arts and predicted the prospects for improving the educational process in Ukrainian institutions of the relevant profile.

In the current context of the development of science, culture and audiovisual arts and production, domestic and foreign scholars have studied various aspects of training specialists in the field of culture and art. At the same time, the problem of

training specialists in the field of audiovisual art and production is quite relevant for most countries and the international community as a whole. The analysis of modern research and scientific publications makes it possible to conclude that the problem of training specialists in the field of audiovisual art and production is quite timely.

Currently, this problem is being considered by: directors – R. Shyrman (2019), O. Bezruchko (2013; 2014a); actors – M. Barnych (2018); producers – O. Moskalenko-Vysotska (2019); announcers and TV program hosts – O. Bezruchko, H. Desiatnyk, M. Ishchenko, S. Poleshko, S. Porozhna (2015); masters of audiovisual art and production – O. Bezruchko, I. Gavran, A. Medvedieva, H. Chmil (2020), etc. However, there is no unified system for determining the results and criteria of the procedure for determining the formation of professional competence and relevant competencies in this field of culture. At the same time, the criteria and indicators for the formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production need to be clarified and further studied.

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the criteria and indicators, as well as professional competencies, for the formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production.

Main research material

The phenomenon of readiness for creative activity is quite thoroughly reflected in psychological and pedagogical research. Thus, O. Bartkiv defines readiness for creative activity as a component of a holistic innovation system and considers it as a multidimensional phenomenon of professional activity that pro-

vides purposeful innovation in the creative process. The scientist believes that “readiness for creative activity is a special personal state that implies the presence of a motivational and value-based attitude to professional activity, possession of effective ways and means of achieving goals, the ability to create and reflect” (Bartkiv, 2010, p.53).

According to V. Uruskyi (2005, p.72), there is a readiness for creative activity, which is manifested “through the ability to identify the most effective methods and ways of introducing innovations, mastery of the implemented technologies, methods, etc.”.

It is worth noting that the dominant factor of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, according to O. Pryadko (2015, p.216), is “the need to transform, improve the work of screenwriters, directors, sound engineers, directors, cameramen using a direct attitude to their profession and the final result of their activities, as well as the perfection of the creative project”.

Given the above, we consider readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production as a complex personal and professional formation that makes it possible for directors, stage managers, screenwriters, artists, musicians and cameramen to focus on the development of their professional activities, as well as activity and independence, creative realization, the introduction of new means, techniques of audiovisual activity that have an innovative focus on the final creative result.

During the preparation and implementation of the audiovisual master's project, they worked with a team that included: a director of photography; a scriptwriter; a composer of music; a production designer; a director of photography.

The formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production was successfully carried out using the capabilities of the training and production TV studio and sound studio within the creative project, including: "Acting", "Film Directing", "Cinematography", "Editing". The preparation of such a creative project was carried out with the help of experienced and less experienced professionals (student assistants) in specially equipped rooms. The effectiveness of the training was positively influenced by organized acting studios in specially equipped rehearsal rooms.

In this approach, in the process of forming readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, it is advisable to adhere to the following criteria: *motivational and value, cognitive and cognitive, and actional and creative*. These criteria are consistent with each other and provide the basis for determining the indicators and levels of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production.

The motivational and value criterion characterizes the motivational attitudes of the individual, the system of motives for choosing a creative project and understanding its value orientations, the level of desire to improve professional training through awareness of the content of the creative activity, its features in the field of audiovisual art and production. As a result of the scientific research, we propose to identify the following indicators of the motivational and value criterion: attitude to the chosen speciality and the desire and ability to self-educate in the field of audiovisual art and production.

The analysis of the results of research activities shows that "the motivational and value criterion stimulates the intellectual and spiritual development of the

individual, the ability to self-development" (Malykhin, 2005, p.29), contributes to the formation of the valuable qualities of the members of the creative project, namely: scriptwriter, director, music composer, production designer and cameraman.

The motivational-value criterion implies a value-based understanding of audiovisual reality, the formation of attitudes, stereotypes, values, images of the world, and the presence of positive internal motivation to understand the goals and objectives that solve the problems of forming readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, purposefulness in mastering professional skills and putting them into practice, the desire for social interaction in the team, and the organization of joint activities.

The cognitive and cognitive criterion reflects the degree of mastery of the body of knowledge necessary for professional activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, is dominant among other groups of criteria, and also consists of the following indicators: the degree of formation of integrative knowledge and skills necessary for the implementation of activities in the field of audiovisual art and production; development of the artistic and associative fund; general intellectual development of the members of the creative project.

As a result of observations of the organization and implementation of the creative project idea, the following indicators of the cognitive and cognitive criterion should be highlighted: implementation of the creative project's concept by a team of like-minded people; creation of conditions that ensure the team's internal readiness to perceive the goals and objectives that contribute to the successful completion of the creative project; mas-

tering a stimulating system of knowledge, moral and ethical principles that contribute to the realization of the team's interests and the solution of the tasks.

The cognitive and learning criterion reflects the attitude to the enrichment and deepening of professional knowledge, the desire to search for it independently, and awareness of the multidimensionality of social factors, mechanisms, and means that affect the personality, the quality of worldview and human knowledge, knowledge of the peculiarities of social interaction with representatives of different social groups in the conditions of freedom of personal choice, strategies and tactics of communication, and knowledge containing information about ways to perform various activities to expand professional knowledge.

The activity-creative criterion is characterized by the ability for inventive problem solving, originality in the director's and production idea, the ability to justify the plot and production concept of the composition of a creative project, the ability to solve production and directorial tasks of increased complexity, an independent approach to planning and selection of interactive technologies by the concept of a creative project (Bartkiv, 2010, p.148).

We propose to diagnose the activity-creative criterion of forming readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production based on the following indicators: the ability to inventive problem solving, originality and creativity in solving problems regarding the script and staging a creative project; creative approach in professional training for the implementation of the author's concept and script by a working group of like-minded people (Uruskyi, 2005, p.38).

The activity-creative criterion determines the level of mastery of the audio-

visual art specialist in the methods of creative activity and reveals the productive and transformative dynamic nature of the audiovisual process, the originality of the interpretation of the script of the creative project, stage and creative improvisation, the introduction of innovative technologies for the implementation of the creative project and the director's flexible combination of the author's idea, forecasting and prediction of the future result.

By the defined indicators of the outlined criteria, we have identified four levels of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production: high, sufficient, medium and initial.

To analyze the approaches to measuring the levels of development of the motivational-value, cognitive-cognitive and activity-creative components of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, the following tools were used: the methodology for choosing a profession by V. Semychenko, the methodology for determining the factors of the attractiveness of the profession by V. Yadov in the modification of N. Kuzmina and A. Rean, the methodology "Value Orientations" by M. Rokich in the modification of Y. Povarenkov. The three-volume collective monograph "Workshop of Film and Television Directors: Teacher and Students" (Bezruchko ed., 2014b) thoroughly examines the specifics and problems of teaching in the creative workshop of film and television directors at one of Kyiv's audiovisual universities from the perspective of both the course leader (master) and, most importantly, the students of this creative workshop.

Therefore, most methods deal with professional values, which certainly influence the formation of readiness for cre-

ative activity in the field of cinema and television.

Thus, audiovisual art and production specialists should have the following competencies to present an appropriate level of audiovisual skills; the ability to carry out editorial and scripting, producing, directing, cameraman and sound engineering activities in the field of audiovisual art and production; the ability to create and implement own concepts in creative and production activities; the ability to interpret the stage and artistic image by audiovisual means; the importance of selecting, composing, purposefully forming and using the information and imaginative levels of an audiovisual project. In addition, to be aware of the interrelationships and interdependencies between the theory and practice of audiovisual art and production; the ability to carry out professional activities using modern achievements in the theory and methodology of audiovisual art and production, taking into account a wide range of interdisciplinary relationships; the ability to collect, analyze and synthesize stage and artistic information and apply it in practical and creative activities; the ability to apply traditional and alternative innovative technologies of film studies, In addition, the ability to carry out and maintain communication with the media to educate, popularize and promote the achievements of screen art, including using the possibilities of radio, television, the Internet; the ability to monitor

promising changes in the field of audiovisual art, using original foreign language sources.

Conclusions

The formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual arts and production is a complex and lengthy process, the effectiveness of which is influenced by certain conditions, factors and factors. Using this approach, we have identified and substantiated the criteria and indicators for the formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of screen arts and real film production, as well as professional competencies that form a holistic structure in which all elements are interdependent and interrelated.

It is proved that in the formation of readiness for creative activity in the field of audiovisual art and production, it is advisable to adhere to criteria that are consistent with each other and give grounds for determining indicators and levels, including motivational and value, cognitive and cognitive, and activity and creative.

The study identified four levels of readiness for creative activity in the field of screen art, namely: high, sufficient, intermediate and beginner.

A promising further development is the development of educational and methodological support for the appropriate training of specialists in the field of audiovisual art and production.

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ФОРМУВАННЯ ГОТОВНОСТІ ДО ТВОРЧОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ У СФЕРІ АУДІОВІЗУАЛЬНОГО МИСТЕЦТВА ТА ВИРОБНИЦТВА

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Анотація

Мета дослідження – дослідити та проаналізувати критерії та показники формування готовності до творчої діяльності у сфері аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва, а саме: мотиваційно-ціннісний, когнітивно-пізнавальний та діяльнісно-творчий. Відповідно до зазначених критеріїв довести фахові компетентності, якими повинен володіти фахівець аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва, що уможливить творчий підхід до професійної діяльності. **Методологія дослідження** полягає у використанні методів емпіричного рівня дослідження – спостереження, рейтинг та самооцінка, колективний консиліум, експеримент, контент-аналіз, узагальнення практичного досвіду, експертна оцінка; методів теоретичного рівня дослідження – експериментальна перевірка нових творчих проєктів, розв'язання інтегрованих завдань, аналітичний, дедуктивний, індуктивний методи, моделювання, порівняння, абстрагування й конкретизації, аналіз і синтез, мисленневий (уявний) експеримент, узагальнення опрацьованого матеріалу. **Наукова новизна:** вперше в теорії і практиці запропоновано та експериментально перевірено критерії та показники формування готовності до творчої діяльності у сфері аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва. **Висновки.** Формування готовності до творчої діяльності у сфері аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва є складним та тривалим процесом, на результативність якого впливають певні умови, фактори та чинники. За такого підходу виділено критерії та показники формування готовності до творчої діяльності у сфері аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва, а також фахові компетентності, що утворюють цілісну структуру, у якій всі елементи взаємозалежать один від одного та є взаємопов'язаними між собою.

Ключові слова: формування готовності до творчої діяльності; аудіовізуальне мистецтво та виробництво; критерії; показники; фахові компетентності; культурологія